

GREEN INVESTMENTS AND THEIR IMPORTANCE IN INDUSTRIAL FIELDS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the notion of “green investment” and its importance to ensure both ecological and economic development of the countries. In the article, the experience of different countries will be discussed and the reasons to implement green economy and green investments will be analyzed.*

Keywords: *green energy, green economy, green investment, renewable energy, carbon emission, ecological well-being.*

Introduction

Idea of green economy is developed from the need for cooperating both ecological and economic growth. This modern notion goes back to 1989 when professional of ecological and economical fields presented their reports in Great Britain. They suggested the idea of green economy and its basic principles in their report, which is considered as a basis for the notion that is being supported nowadays.

This report suggested that economical system should consider ecological factors and condition, otherwise ecological well-being would get even worse. The idea suggested spread to other institutions and considered necessary. Over the following years organizations such as UN, World Bank, EU, Asian Development bank supported this idea. For example, in 2011 the organization of United Nations in its ecological program called “Green Economy: Pathways to sustainable development and poverty eradication” defined the notion of green energy and green economy in details to support it further.

It is said that “A green economy is a system that increases economic well-being based on the efficient use of resources, ensuring social justice, and significantly reducing environmental risks”. this means that green economy, unlike traditional economy, is not focused on only earning benefit, but environmental protection, social justice, renewing energy sources and sustaining opportunities for future generations. For this reason, in recent years scientists are working in this field. One of them is R. Constanza, who introduced the term “services of ecosystem” which means the relation between economic growth and ecological systems. Moreover, Nicholas Stern studied the effect of climate change on economy, and suggested investing more on ecological issues to ease the situation. The implementation of green energy projects have some problems which may make the process difficult, and for this reason, several countries are working together in cooperation to solve the problems so that the future of economy and their development can be sustained.

Main part

Nowadays green economy is considered as an alternative way to cope with climate change, lack of resources, environmental pollution and extinction of biological diversity. This system reflects such areas as increasing energy efficiency, using renewable energy sources, recycling

waste, introducing environmentally friendly technologies, and creating “green” jobs, which means environmentally-friendly vacancies, new fields possibly caused by the introduction and popularity of green energy. Such an approach not only ensures environmental sustainability, but also increases the opportunities for increasing economic efficiency, improving social well-being, and creating sustainable jobs. Thus, the analysis of the literature shows that the green economy is a modern, effective, and sustainable model that needs to be introduced into the national economic system.

In global economy maintaining ecological sustainability and tackling with climate change is considered as the most severe issues nowadays. Industrial sectors are considered as a central field which is a main source of energy consumption and greenhouse gases. For this reason, green investments are necessary to modernize industry to adapt the trending patterns. One of the pioneers, Nicholas Stern, suggested according to his studies that “combating climate change does not limit economic growth, but rather creates new investment opportunities” (2007). This can prove strategic importance of green economy.

Green investments are financial resources that are dedicated to introduce environmentally-friendly technologies, reduce carbon emissions and increase energy efficiency. OECD conducted a research studying green investments. Its experts interpret green investments as “the financial basis for the transition to a low-carbon and resource-efficient economy” (2017). moreover, the head of the International energy agency, Fatih Birol mentioned that in the energy system the directions of investments will determine the structure of economy for the future (2023).

A number functions are performed by green investments in industrial sectors. One of them is that it can increase energy efficiency. According to the “Porter hypothesis” by Michael Porter Claes van der Linde, environmental standards are green investments can develop innovative activity of enterprises, and strengthen their competitiveness. Moreover, it can reduce carbon emission. This was mentioned by Joseph Stiglitz in 2019. He noted that green investments are a necessary condition to sustain economic growth. Finally, it can accelerate technological innovations in the field of industry as a result of new energy sources and methods to process them. This is associated with the concept of “green growth, which refers to the combination of economic growth and ecological balance.

A number of countries around the world can prove the efficiency and the importance of green investment. For example, in Germany green energy was implemented under the policy of “Energiewende”, which directed high investments to the renewable energy sources.

In China nowadays, for example, the field of producing green energy technologies is considered as a leading sector, which ranks China high among the other countries. According to the reports of IRENA (International Renewable Energy Agency) in 2022, China is the country which is allocating majority of investments to the field of renewable energy sources. In the USA to promote green investment and energy resources taxation policies and subsidies are being implemented. In the case of Uzbekistan, there are important policies related to the implementation of green energy. For example, the projects promoting solar and wind stations to sustain electric energy are being proposed. Foreign organizations such as WB and ADB are cooperating to invest in green economy and energy projects to help the country.

Conclusion

In conclusion, green investments are an important factor in modernizing industry, ensuring environmental sustainability, and stimulating economic growth.

Green economy is a modern economic model based on the principles of environmental protection, social equality and economic sustainability, aimed at the efficient use of resources and the preservation of the potential of natural systems for future generations. In the current context of globalization, this direction is becoming one of the main factors of sustainable development. The Republic of Uzbekistan is also implementing systemic reforms in this direction. In particular, state strategies developed on the basis of the “Green Economy” concept, initiatives to increase energy efficiency, introduce renewable energy sources, recycle waste and switch to environmentally friendly technologies are yielding positive results.

The transition to a green economy will increase the competitiveness of the Uzbek economy, improve people’s health and living standards, and provide an opportunity to find effective solutions to global problems such as resource scarcity, climate change, and environmental pollution. The main condition for this is to ensure a balance between economic growth, social well-being, and environmental sustainability.

Scientific research shows that the transition to a green economy is not only an environmental necessity, but also an economic opportunity. Therefore, expanding green investments and their deep integration into industry in Uzbekistan is of strategic importance.

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